

Editor Note

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Editor Note

After the success of our previous issue of our New Journal, we are coming out with newer articles with our next issue. We have had great applications and expect to keep getting outstanding articles from around the academic world. We acknowledge the authors of the articles from our first issue and the next one. We are great full to all the researchers who have submitted and hope to help them in their effort to get their good work out. As we cannot reinforce it enough the Journal of Gastrointestinal Cancer and Stromal Tumors is all into making an open access comprehensive forum for GI tumors related academic and clinical publications.

In our last note, we had discussed the works of Marwah (Rohtak, India), Sakuraba (Shizuoka, Japan), Shoshita (Oita, Japan), Ahmed (Örebro, Sweden) and Dilsiz (Istanbul, Turkey). The authors Marwah's presentation on spontaneous small bowel perforation showed unusual complications of chemotherapy. Sauraba showed an uncommon location of the tumor following the behavior of its more common cousin the Gastric MALTomas. Shoshita's study on using Supra Pancreatic Lymph nodes as an independent prognostic marker. Ahmed's work delineated how decreased expression of claudins showed poorer clinical outcomes. Dilsiz's work on miRNAs in Colorectal Cancer helps subcategorize them with better prognostication and management [1].

Since then we have published Kazuhito Mita's "Efficacy of Cytoreductive Surgery with Systemic Chemotherapy for Gastric Cancer with Peritoneal Dissemination". A detailed study showing cytoreductive surgery followed by systemic chemotherapy is not an independent prognostic factor for patients with peritoneal dissemination. It reconfirms that the detection of distant metastasis before surgery correlates with poor prognosis [2,3].

Dr. Anu Behari and Vinay Kumar Kapoor's review of reclassification of AJCC for Gall Bladder Cancer is an essential point as the 7th edition is fraught with deficiencies. GBCA is an unknown disease in the developed western world, while it remains a common malignancy in many parts of the world. Adding granularity to the AJCC classification

and adding nonTNM data including genomic and proteomic data would be able to prognosticate and manage the disease better. With the 8th Edition of AJCC out and being implemented from 2018. Lot more data will be entered to fine tune the staging system in Gallbladder Cancer.

In Dr. Bouras's paper from Santorini, Greece it shows an innovative pilot trial of introducing a therapeutic solution of the "anti-sense" proteins in the cancer cell, with the concurrent lowering of body temperature of the patient. The crystallization of the racemic mixture, subsequent expansion of the cytoplasm and rupture of the cancer cell membrane is hypothesized. Lots of studies, including clinical and preclinical trials would need to be done before considering this modality in any form of therapy [4,5].

Dr. Prado's from Long Branch, USA showed an indolent Gastrointestinal Neuroectodermal Tumor of the Colon. This unusual presentation and detailed workup showed unusual pathology presents uniquely and should be considered at all times.

References

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